

Qualitative Study on Chemistry Education for Repositioning Good Governance, Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria: a Systematic Review

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Abstract

The article is a systematic review that focuses on the role of chemistry education in shaping good governance, promoting sustainable development, and driving economic growth. Through a qualitative analysis, this study aims to explore the current state of chemistry education and its impacts on these important factors. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into how chemistry education can be repositioned to better support good governance, sustainable development and economic growth. By examining relevant literature, this study will identify key themes and trends in the field of chemistry education and its intersection with these vital areas. This systematic review has the potential to inform policy decisions and drive future research in the field of chemistry education and its role in promoting societal progress. This paper underlines some recommendations which include development of national chemistry education strategy, increased investment in research and development, and promotion of public-private collaborations. The paper finally suggests increased government presence and funding coupled with the establishment of standard research laboratories in all institutions of learning, adequate and regular local and international capacity building for chemistry teachers among others as way out. Nigeria can take advantage of potential economic benefits of chemistry education and, in turn, achieve greater good governance and economic development.

Keywords: Chemistry, Chemistry Education. Economic Development, Good Governance

Introduction

Science and technology make immense contributions to the material wellbeing of any country, if certain requisites are met. But in most developing countries, lack of scientific and technological knowledge is often a critical limitation to economic progress (Ige, 2013). This fact is borne out by the experiences of developing countries which are ready to acquire, adopt and apply techniques derived from scientific knowledge. There is a clear need to improve on science subjects in our schools, if the country is to meet the rising expectations of the people. With the goal to increase the materials wellbeing of the expanding population, there is a need to improve in scientific knowledge. Therefore, all students at all levels of education must have unrestricted access to the knowledge of science to gain insight into the foundation of many of the achievements of humanity (Emendu, 2014). The keywords chemistry, education, good governance and economic development are defined accordingly as Chemistry is typically an investigative and experimental science involving the study of nature and properties of all forms of matter coupled with the changes these matters undergo under different conditions (Bugaje, 2013). Education is the process of training and institution especially of children and young people in school and colleges which is designed to give knowledge and develop skills (Erinsho, 2005).

Chemistry education plays a vital pivotal role in the overall development of a nation. It's not a subject confined to textbooks but has a profound impact on various aspects of society.

Objectives of the study

The current study aimed to highlight the role of chemistry education for repositioning good governance, sustainable economic growth and development in Nigeria.

1. To highlight the role of chemistry education in nation economic growth
2. To review the importance of chemistry education in repositioning a good governance
3. To highlight the role of chemistry education for sustainable development

Material and method

Search strategy

To carry out this review we the researchers explored search out the articles from various databases. Literature review is a method of collecting data in a way looking for information through books, newspapers, magazines, and other literature. The review articles in the research sourced from several journal studies related to chemistry education and its economic impact as well as role of good governance. Furthermore, the keywords included: Chemistry, education, chemistry education, good governance and economic impacts.

Conceptual Systematic Literature Review

Conceptual Systematic Literature Review

Nature of Chemistry Concept and Chemistry Education in Nigeria

Chemistry has been one of the cornerstones of science, technology and industry, it is apparent that chemistry plays a greater role in national development through industry in the world. As such it helps to provide some social amenities and has been the pivot of science and hence the most needed tool, scientifically, for human, capital and economic development. The concept of chemistry as a science is centered on life and this encompasses the three states of matter-solid, liquid and gas in a give and take processes (Bugaje, 2013). According to Uwague and Ojebah (2008), chemistry is one of the naturally and well-established means through which the nation's abundant natural resources can be harnessed into useful ventures for the overall economic and socio-political wellbeing of its citizenry. Okieimen (2007) equally asserted that chemistry is all about everything in the world. He added that chemistry is the nucleus of science which ultimately is the foundation upon which any nation is developed. Chemistry certainly cannot be divorced from any today human activities (Muhammad, 2009).

Education is a tool for social and economic empowerment and a means of developing qualities in a rich and fulfilled life. The worth status of an individual level and the development of every society depend on the quality of education invested. Hence, educational development became the major criterion for measuring overall national development (Muhammad, Yusha'u & Lawal, 2018). Adesola (2015) states that education is a process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, and directed research. Further he stated that education frequently takes place under the guidance of educators, but learners may also educate themselves. Education is performing two majors' functions in advanced industrial societies transmitting the shared values of society and simultaneously the specialized skills for an Economy development.

Chemistry education is the study of the teaching and learning of chemistry in all schools, colleges and universities. Chemistry education also includes the understanding of how students learn chemistry, how best to teach chemistry, and how to improve learning outcomes by changing teaching methods and appropriate training of chemistry instructors (Okon, 2008). Moreover, Chemistry Education has been identified to be one of the major bedrock for the transformation of a nation's economy. It is needed for the production of the needed technologists, technicians, engineers, medical practitioners who are required to turn the nation's economy around and usher in the desired technological advancement which is very much required for sustainable development (Uwague & Ojebah, 2008). Chemistry Education is the study of the teaching and learning of chemistry in schools. It is concerned with the impartment of knowledge on properties, components, transformations, and interactions of matter. Chemistry Education fosters scientific literacy. Chemical knowledge and the application of chemical principles and products are important in problem-solving. Scientifically literate citizens are an asset to a nation. A chemically literate citizen knows the dangers associated with drugs and how to use them without occasioning harm. (Yusuf *et al.*, 2018). What many nations like Nigeria need now is a functional chemistry education that will assist in national development. Chemistry education has been identified to be one of the major bedrock for the transformation of our national economy (Emmanuel, 2013).

Concept of Influence of Chemistry Education on Good Governance in Nigeria

Good governance is a system of government based on good leadership, respect for the rule of law and due process, the accountability of the political leadership to the electorate as well as transparency in the operations of government (Odock, 2006). It is governance that provokes and defines the nature of security. When there is governance failure, the security frame

work deteriorates. Good governance is able to provide growth and structural change which result in development. Such structure includes schools, judiciary, military, and parliament. When the resulted structural change performs their roles properly, there will be security and the good governance will further be enhanced. Governance is defined as "the way in which socio-economic power is exercised in managing affairs within a nation" (Manu, 2002). In this light, governance of education implies the way in which education institutions affairs is managed within the developing nations. In order to achieve this, rule of law must be adherent to in totality. Rules and policies must guide any governance of education system and made enforceable by all and sundries within the system. The issue of governance is very critical to the development, sustenance and advancement of chemistry education especially at the both secondary and tertiary level. This is because good governance holds the key to good performance and sustainability of education institutions (Obanya, 2003). There is a linear relationship between good governance and a functional chemistry education. There cannot be a functional chemistry education where country's resources and power are not well utilized for the citizen of the nation. Florence et al. (2015) viewed governance as the use of state resources and power in an accountable way to achieve and promote the well-being of the citizenry. It therefore, implies that when the power and resources are not well managed for the welfare of the citizen, there is bound to be a problem

Influence of Chemistry Education for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

There is no doubt that Nigeria is endowed with enormous human and natural resources. As rightly observed by Matthew-Danial (2013), human and natural resources endowment are not enough for wealth creation and economic development of any nation, but the knowledge of how these raw materials can be transformed into valuable goods and services for economic development and improved quality of life. Modern science education holds the key to the rapid transformation of Nigeria. The Nigerian economy is one of the most developed economies in Africa (Economy watch content (EWC, 2010). It has been observed that Nigeria is a middle-income nation with developed financial and communication among others and that Nigeria has the second largest stock exchange market in the African continent (EWC, 2010).

Chemistry education plays a pivotal role in the overall development of a nation. It is not a subject confined laboratories and textbooks but has profound impacts on various aspects of society. It plays the major roles in food (fertilizers and insecticides), clothing (textile fibers), housing (cement, concrete, steel, bricks), Medicine (drugs), Transportation (fuel, alloy materials). Presently, man is experiencing an era in scientific and technological development that affects his life in one way or the other. Virtually everything we use daily involves science (Yusuf, *et al.*, 2018).

Chemistry education holds immense importance in national development. By enhancing scientific knowledge and research capabilities, addressing environmental challenges, and meeting industrial demands, chemistry education becomes a driving force for progress. It empowers individuals to make meaningful contributions to society, fostering innovation, and paving the way for brighter future. Therefore, investing in chemistry education is essential for a nations overall growth and prosperity.

Achieving a high level of economic development through transforming the country real sectors will not only reduce poverty by providing food security, increased in agricultural and industrial exports, but will also bring about improved literacy and a healthy workforce. Chemical research has contributed to economic prosperity and financial security in the country. Products from chemical companies, such as polymers, coatings, pharmaceuticals, and pesticides, play an important role in everyday life. The chemical production companies have a large portion of various specialists who have contribute to the development of the country (Ekpo, 1993). Over the years chemistry has contributed through the following measures, which have helped in the economic development of many nations. These measures are

Enhancing Scientific Knowledge and Research for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry education paves the way for a nation's scientific progress by imparting the fundamental knowledge required for scientific research. By understanding the principles, theories, and laws governing chemical reactions, aspiring chemists can delve into cutting edge research and make groundbreaking discoveries. Such research has the potential to revolutionize various sectors, from health care to agriculture, and boost the nation's development. For instance, the discovery of new drugs or materials through chemistry research can significantly impact the pharmaceutical industry, leading to better healthcare outcomes and economic growth.

1. Chemistry education equips individuals with a solid foundation in scientific principles and concepts.
2. It fosters critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities necessary for research and innovation.
3. Promoting research and advancements in chemistry leads to the development of new materials, medicines and technologies that benefit society as a whole.

Addressing Environmental Challenges for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry education has a significant role to play in addressing the pressing environmental challenges facing the world today. By instilling a sense of environmental responsibility and emphasizing sustainable practices, chemist can contribute to preserving and protecting the environment.

Understanding the chemical processes behind pollution or climate change enables experts to devise innovative solutions and develop environmentally friendly technologies. This not only benefits the nation's ecological balance but also creates opportunities for economic growth through the emergence of clean energy industry.

1. Chemistry education emphasizes the importance of sustainable development practices and environmental awareness.
2. It equips individuals with the knowledge to develop greener technologies and mitigate environmental hazards.
3. Chemist with a strong educational background can contribute to solutions for pollution, waste management, and climate change.

Meeting industrial demand for sustainable economic growth and development in Nigeria

A robust chemistry education system plays a vital role in meeting the demands of the industrial sector. From pharmaceuticals to petrochemicals, numerous industries rely on chemists and chemical engineers to drive innovation and production. By equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge, chemistry education facilitates the development of a skilled workforce capable of meeting the industry's requirements. A skilled chemistry workforce not only contributes to economic growth but also enhances a nation's competitiveness in global market.

1. Chemistry education prepares individuals for careers in various industrial sectors
2. It provides the necessary skills and knowledge to cater the demands of industries such as pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and materials.
3. A well-educated chemistry workforce fuels economic growth and enhance a nations competitiveness in global market.

Chemistry Entrepreneurial Skill for sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry entrepreneurial education has the potential of changing the fortune of a nation and transforming it from under developed to a developing and subsequently developed country. A chemist is an entrepreneur and an entrepreneur is a person who evaluates business opportunities, gather necessary resources and initiate appropriate action to ensure success (Wushishi, 2013). The success of Nigeria in the 21st century, its wealth and welfare will depend on the ideas and entrepreneurial skills of its population. These have always been the nation most important assets (Iyun, 2013). Achieving chemistry entrepreneurial skills produce chemists who will create new ideas, new products and entirely new industries.

Innovation and Modernization for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Technological innovation is dependent on chemistry education because, through chemistry researches, newer and better methods of production are discovered for improved productivity. In addition, chemistry stimulates motivation and widens inquisitiveness. Furthermore, chemistry liberates the mind from the vestige of ignorance and superstition and makes a man willing to accept change. Chemistry widens man's ideas and outlook; it breaks man conservatism and prepares the mind to accept modern and improved ideas and techniques. In the developed world, chemistry through its innovativeness has helped to transform indigenous technology for the holistic development of their countries.

Income Distribution for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Efficient income distribution is a prerequisite for equity, rapid national growth, social and political stability. These can only be achieved if chemistry plays its role not necessarily in bridging the gap between the rich and the poor but in the redistribution of income between the people in the country. Thurow in Kene and Oguji (1997) rightly observed that an increase in the educational level of low-income workers is bound to have some beneficial benefit, including, increase in productivity and a consequent increase in earning, reduction in the number of low skill workers, which lead to an increase in their wages and increase in the number of high skill workers.

Agriculture for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemical principles and products have been utilized to control pests and weeds and in fertilizer production for increased food production. Genetically improved crops based on pest protection. is used to improve crop production. The herbicide tolerance (HT) crops are tolerant to certain broad-spectrum herbicides such as glyphosate and glufosinate, which are more effective, less toxic, and usually cheaper than selective herbicides. By cutting the costs and labor of weed or insect control, these first-generation commercial pests and/or herbicide-tolerant crops have been shown to provide a tangible economic benefit to farmers. It is therefore critical that chemistry students be exposed to appropriate knowledge of chemistry in the areas of agrochemicals and chemical-based technologies to boost agricultural production environmental and economic sustainability of food security.

Contribution to Improved Health and Sanitation Facilities for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Drugs, which are products of chemistry abound and are used for various purposes including prevention and treatment of various diseases. Proserpine, a Yohimbe alkaloid, for example, has important clinical use in the treatment of high blood pressure (hypertension) and also as a tranquillizer for the emotionally disturbed. Ergot alkaloids are used chemically to induce contraction of the uterus in the last stages of pregnancy. Morphine and compounds are well-known pain relievers (Aniodoh, 2001).

Potable Water Supply for Sustainable Economic Growth and development in Nigeria

Water is chemically treated to kill germs, thus rendering it fit for human consumption and other domestic use. Chemical processes are exceptionally important in the treatment and delivery of drinking water and the treatment of wastewater. Analytical techniques (including the development of associated portable devices) are critical in verifying the quality of water, and where required chemicals and membranes are employed in simple disinfection treatment. Chemical science also plays a significant role in the remediation of the aquatic environment following pollution incidents. Chemistry research within the water sector is therefore playing a vital role in the transformations that are needed to achieve a sustainable freshwater supply, both domestically and on a global scale. Fundamental chemistry research is a necessary condition to support strategies that will provide the technological solutions needed to deliver new and improved methods of optimizing water use, treating contaminated water, recycling water, desalination water and preserving water in the soil, and harvesting water for irrigation (Odedokun & Abubakar, 2017).

Clothing for sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Some textile fibers used as clothing are obtained by modifying natural fibers of agricultural origin such as viscose rayon and cellulose acetate from cellulose. Other fibers such as nylons, ethylene, and acrylic fibers are all chemical synthetic derivatives from petroleum sources and are used as clothing (Okenyi *et al.*, 2011).

Energy Supply for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Coal is fuel and a source of energy. Fuel derived from petroleum is used to power automobiles, airplanes and ships. Gaseous fuel such as butane is used as cooking gas. Kerosene, a derivative of petroleum, is a household name and is used in heating, cooking and lighting (Aniodoh, 2001). Chemistry Education provides solutions to our problems in the energy sector by developing sustainable biofuels (e.g. through optimization of biochemical conversion processes as well as thermochemical conversion and gasification process (Odedokun & Abubakar, 2017).

Major Areas of Influence of Bad Governance on Chemistry Education

The lack of good governance is impacting Nigeria educational system badly in all areas. However, there are specific areas it seriously affects chemistry education. The paper considers six critical areas. These are:

Research in Chemistry

Research in the Nigerian universities has been rendered useless because of the paucity of fund. The government has money to build personal houses for the government officials but no money for research. They also have money to sponsor political party campaign and rally. Many of them are so naïve to have gone as far as buying properties in the developed countries and had bank accounts in foreign countries but no money for educational research. Most educational research institutes are mere names but can do nothing. Corruption of our government officials had killed and buried research in chemistry and science

education for decades. Because of corruption resources from the national treasury meant for research are in the hands of a few individuals who are politically powerful (Otoghile *et al.*, 2014).

Teachers' Education and training

Teachers Education and Training in Nigeria is very poor when compared with other developing countries in Africa. Due to the lack of sound teacher education and training in Nigeria, the teaching and learning of science are perceived difficult by both the teachers and the students. Most teachers lack adequate pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) for science teaching. Many students at the end of their Junior Secondary School (JSS) preferred Art and Humanities courses to Science. Given the havoc the insurgency had caused to the Nigerian socio-economic development in the recent time by our youth, lack of governance is a menace in the nation. Many of these insurgents are science oriented that could be useful to this nation, but we lost them to the insurgency. These youth used improvised materials, and other complex weapon produced by themselves: these are great scientists.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure in the Nigerian educational institutions is in a terrible condition. It is worrisome and nasty for students to learn science under the tree in some part of the nation today. This is a reflection of the poor budgetary allocation to education by the government. Good governance requires that enough funds be made available for all educational programmes. The Nigeria experience shows that poor budgetary allocation to education is meager, and this against the UNESCO recommendations of 26% of the total allocation to the education sector (Akindutire and Ekundayo, 2010).

A visit to some of the Nigerian universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education reveals that the Nigerian government is not serious about education. There are poor office accommodations for lecturers and working conditions. Science is a cognitive course that requires a conducive environment for its teaching and learning.

Inadequate Manpower

A significant problem faced with science and chemistry education in Nigeria today is the issue of inadequate manpower. It is doubtful if Nigeria has sufficient and qualified number of indigenous science and chemistry teachers. This has in no small way hindered the growth of chemistry education and by extension affected self-reliance and national development. In most of the tertiary institutions, the number of senior lecturers with Ph.D qualifications is low. Rather, we have most of them in the cadre of Assistant lecturers, Graduate Assistant and lecturer III-I. These crops of lecturers are still learning the rudiments of teaching by the reason of their qualifications and training (Uwague and Ojebah, 2008, Emumejaye, 2006). Only few of those in the professional rank are available. Poor salary scale/remuneration is equally associated with teaching job in Nigeria compared with the elected/politically appointed officers. This has led to long period of strike actions by teaching and non-teaching personnel across the educational sector. Teachers reward against all odds is often said to be in Heaven. These are negative factors on the growth of chemistry education, self-reliance and national development. The quality of education rests more on the quality of its teachers (Akubudike, 2003).

Associated Hazards

No sane person will live his home for work and anticipate accident. The greatest inherent problem associated with chemistry and its education is hazard. Hazard effects from poisonous emission of gases/ fumes, corrosive chemicals, fire burnt, explosion, obsolete apparatus, poor laboratory sanitary condition etc. are very often recorded in chemistry laboratory, lack of safety awareness due to unsafe acts and unsafe working conditions results to accidents. Victims of chemicals or fire burnt usually present ugly scenes. Often times, large casualties are recorded when accident occur in the field of chemistry. This cannot promote chemistry education, good governance and economic development.

Defective Curriculum

School curriculum in the pre-independent Nigeria was not for all-round development of the child as the aspects of science and technology which would have created entrepreneurial skills for self-reliance were ignored (Sabina, 2009). It rather kept on producing subservient Nigerians who were tied to the apron string of white-collar jobs viz: gardeners, stewards, interpreters, catechists, clerks and house-keepers. All these make the people parasitic consumers rather than creative and efficient producers. The curriculum for science and chemistry education in particular is such that is over loaded with much emphasis on theoretical teaching. There is an obvious relationship between development and the type of educational structures available in any country (Sabina, 2009).

Conclusion

This paper provides an insight into the role and importance of chemistry education for national development in Nigeria; Objectives of chemistry education in the Nigerian education system are also part of the discussion in this paper.

Chemistry education is important for the production of manpower in Nigeria's labour market. Chemistry education is needed for development, technological emancipation and industrial expansion. Chemistry education enhances skill acquisition and application, Chemistry Education includes the propagation of the teaching and learning of chemistry and empowers students by exposing them to entrepreneurship programmes in which they can make choices in life and become self-employed.

Recommendations

From the fore going, it is quite obvious to say that if these factors among others are well tackled, Nigeria would have started laying concrete foundation towards becoming a first world developed nation.

Chemistry education requires a well-designed and equipped laboratory to achieve its primary goals of observation and investigation. A functioning laboratory is such that have the most basic facilities like power and water supply, chemical reagents and apparatus, current analytical instruments, adequate space and ventilation. The laboratory should also be manned by a highly skilled and competent technologist, for effective and rewarding application. This will enhance self-reliance and national development.

The enhanced concrete foundation should start at the primary school level. Since primary education is seen as the bedrock of all forms of education in any nation, Nigeria should not be left out (Umoh 2007). Every Nigerian child has the right to proper education and even science education. At this level, teaching should be based on demonstration and all participatory learning.

Science and chemistry education in particular will be meaningless for selfreliance and national development if the qualities of the teachers cannot be guaranteed. Chemistry education requires specialist, competent and dedicated teachers. To ensure self-reliance and national development, chemistry teachers should be given appropriate professional training by professional bodies. Science and chemistry teachers should be trained and retrained through seminars, workshops, and conferences on innovative teaching.

Teachers and students are to be well educated of the need to be safety conscious especially in the laboratory at all times. Prevention is often said to be a better cure from an accident. Precaution signs should be pasted/posted at strategic positions in the laboratory. The laboratory should also be well illuminated and ventilated coupled with strategically located firefighting equipment.

School curriculum in the sciences, particularly chemistry should be reviewed and restructured to meet up with the need and aspirations of the people. A curriculum that is practically driven and achievable should be put in place. Members of the curriculum drafting committee should be drawn from professional bodies like the Chemical Society of Nigeria (CSN), Institute of Chartered Chemists of Nigeria (ICCON),etc, to enable them restructure the curriculum with the view of meeting the present day reality

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